

**Fostering Improved Training Tools
For Responsible Research and Innovation
FIT4RRI**

Experiment 4 Report

Text and Data Mining Big Scholarly Data
(Deliverable 3.4)

Due by: August 31st 2019

Deliverable Responsible: The Open University

Status: PU

Release 1.0

Function	Staff	Delivery date
Prepared by	Nancy Pontika, Petr Knoth, Bikash Gyawali	16 August 2019
1 st Draft Delivered by	Nancy Pontika, Petr Knoth, Bikash Gyawali	16 August 2019
Reviewed by	Nikos Zaharis, SEERC	27 August 2019
Submitted to EU by	Andrea Riccio, UNIROMA	09 September 2019

Table of Contents

Definitions.....	3
Executive summary.....	4
1. Experiment description	4
1.1. Organizer.....	4
1.2. Aim & objectives	4
1.3. Selected RRI pillars	5
2. Internal stakeholders description	5
3. External stakeholders description	5
4. First meeting outcome summary	6
5. Second meeting outcome summary.....	9
6. Third meeting outcome summary.....	9
7. Fourth meeting outcome summary	18
8. Lessons learnt.....	18
8.1. Main blockers of quadruple helix co-creation	18
8.2. Proposed consensus strategies & co-creation approaches/frameworks.....	19
8.3. Most relevant RRI practices (from WP1 and WP2) for the experiment	19
8.4. Institutional changes required to fully embed the chosen RRI pillars	19
8.5. Policy support/changes required to properly embed RRI in the ongoing research with the involvement of the quadruple helix	19
8.6. Any issues/constraints noticed during the experiment implementation (i.e. procedural issues)	20
9. Next steps.....	20
Appendix A – Workshop	21
Appendix B – Experiment KPIs.....	21

Definitions

Text and Data Mining (TDM): the process of extracting high quality and meaningful information from text to answer unknown questions.

Big Scholarly Data: Big Data is the Information asset characterised by a High Volume, Velocity and Variety to require specific Technology and Analytical Methods for its transformation into Value.

Open Access (OA): it refers to online, free of cost access to peer reviewed scientific content with limited copyright and licensing restrictions.

Closed Access: it refers to scientific content which is locked behind a paywall and requires either a subscription or purchase.

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI): a transparent and interactive process that spans and acknowledges mutual responsibility across different actors.

Executive summary

Staff and students affiliated to a university can access and download all the research papers the institution subscribes to, provided that they are logged in to the institution's network. While readers can access research literature their university subscribes to quite easily, it is not possible for text and data miners to machine access research literature their university subscribes to effectively and at scale.

The current amendments and exceptions in the Copyright Law have given us the green light to text and data mine (TDM) content we have acquired access to for non-commercial research. eduTDM aims to find a pragmatic solution to arrange how this content can be delivered to text miners as easily as possible based on the subscription they have.

In order to reach to a pragmatic solution and examine whether the stakeholders agree with the eduTDM vision, the Open University (OU) created a working group (WG) consisting of commercial closed access publishers, open access publishers, companies performing TDM, organisations creating TDM corpuses, policy makers, text and data miners and industry (see more on sections 3 - 7 below).

1. Experiment description

This experiment has conducted three online meetings with the working group members (see section 3) and these meetings were recorded (see Appendix). In these meetings, both the researchers and the stakeholders had equal opportunities to express their opinions on the topic. In some meetings the researchers had prepared and addressed specific open ended and closed ended questions (see section 4), while in other meetings (see sections 5,6 and 7) the conversations were shaped based on the feedback the researchers received from the working group members.

1.1. Organizer

The organiser of this co-experiment is The Open University (OU).

1.2. Aim & objectives

This working group is consisted of a variety of stakeholders, such as the publishing industry, text and data mining scientific community, digital infrastructures representatives and policy makers. More specifically, this working group aims to:

- Initiate and establish a collaboration and a communication route between a range of stakeholders on this topic.
- Define, discuss and disseminate the principles and views of the stakeholders involved in this collaboration.

- Understand the position of the stakeholders on eduTDM.
- Establish a development plan for putting eduTDM into practice.

1.3. Selected RRI pillars

The selected RRI pillars are:

- Open Access
- Open Science
- Governance

2. Internal stakeholders description

The experiment is being conducted by including the following internal stakeholders from the Open University: Petr Knoth, Nancy Pontika and Bikash Gyawali. There are no other internal stakeholders involved in this co-experiment.

3. External stakeholders description

As it is described in section 1.2 the OU initiated and established a collaboration with key stakeholders who would define, discuss and disseminate the principles and position of stakeholders and establish the development plan for putting eduTDM into practice.

More specifically, the group members of the eduTDM working group are:

- Experts in publisher systems
 - Duncan Campbell - Wiley
 - Vicky Gardner - Taylor and Francis
 - Melissa Harrison - eLife
 - Victoria Eva - Elsevier
- Experts in TDM
 - Viktor Botev - IRIS.AI
 - Jacobo Elosua - IRIS.AI
- Experts in making recommendations and spreading best practices
 - Kathleen Shearer - Confederation of Open Access Repositories
 - Rachel Bruce - Jisc
- Experts in industry
 - Roland Strauss - Knowledge4Innovation

4. First meeting outcome summary

During the first meeting we explored the area and sought organisational and technical challenges and opportunities. During the first meeting of the eduTDM WG, which took place on the 4th of October 2018, it was proposed that one or more trusted entities in the UK should be able to provide/broker large scale machine access to all content, from across multiple publishers for TDM purposes. The purpose of this effort would be to benefit of staff or students at an institution that has lawful access to this content, thanks to the institution's subscription or due to the content being available through the open access route. We then asked this WG for feedback.

The closed ended questions asked were:

1. Do you believe that text mining has the potential to help us improve the way in which research is conducted?

2. Are you aware that everyone in the UK is currently allowed to perform TDM for research purposes?

3. Do you believe that UK affiliated researchers should be able to gather data to perform TDM on all content their university subscribes to?

5

4. Do you agree that it is still a challenge for UK affiliated researchers to gather all research papers their university subscribes to?

4

5. Do you support the idea that there should be just one trusted authorisation layer enabling to gather content for TDM?

4

The open-ended questions asked were:

- A. What technical challenges do you foresee in establishing TDM?
- B. What organisational challenges do you foresee in establishing TDM?
- C. What is the greatest issue to overcome in establishing TDM?

With regards to the results, all WG participants mentioned that they are aware of the many possibilities and benefits emerging from TDM (Q1), while not all of them were aware of the recent Copyright Exception in the UK, which is limited to research only and not commercial use (Q2). For this question there was a discussion about the word ‘lawful’, as this word was missing from the question given, but is mentioned in the updated legislation prohibiting the use of content to those who do not have a subscription. In addition, the WG participants responded positively and strongly to the third question (Q3).

All WG members agreed that there are challenges for the universities in collecting the lawful content for TDM (Q4), and there were concerns about the idea of “one trusted authorisation layer” that enables the creation of a corpus for TDM purposes (Q5). A clarification was then provided, highlighting that goal was to implement one trusted protocol or process, rather than having only one entity that acts in this area. A member of this WG is affiliated with an open access publisher (eLife) and commented that the open access content should become available from more than one place and it was clarified that this initiative’s focus is not on open access.

In the open-ended questions, the WG participants had the opportunity to provide input by adding free text. The primary focus of these questions was the challenges in putting the eduTDM idea in place and brainstorming on how this process could be implemented. The responses with regards to the technical challenges (QA) mentioned a paper’s format, i.e. PDF, XML, HTML, the lack of common standards for metadata, data and APIs and the need for an agreement on them, managing subscriptions, and lack of a common registry of API subscriptions at an institutional level.

The responses on organisational challenges (QB) relate to the incentives that the publishing industry should consider adopting the service and agree on common standards, burden sharing, e.g. infrastructural costs, perceived benefits, common legal frameworks, gaining traction. When the WG participants were asked to provide their comments on a single and perhaps the greatest challenge (QC), their responses focused more on the organisational challenges than the technical. This indicates, that even though a technical solution is possible, it is the organisational challenges that would have a negative impact on the progress of this initiative.

To conclude, the WG participants are in favour of eduTDM, understand its capabilities and benefits, and are keen on the idea that researchers affiliated with a UK university should take advantage of the recent amendment in the UK copyright law. They all agree that currently researchers affiliated with a university face challenges in the lawful collection of a large corpus of data for TDM purposes and one or more trusted entities could possibly provide a solution. Nonetheless, there are many technical challenges, such as standards and formatting, and

organisational, such as infrastructural costs and gaining traction, with the most difficult appearing to be the organisational ones.

It was discussed and agreed that the CORE Team, which has proposed the eduTDM concept and has put the WG together to discuss this topic, will now focus on drafting a proposal for addressing the technical challenges, as presented in the below section, demonstrating how the eduTDM vision can be technically realised.

5. Second meeting outcome summary

In the second meeting we explored how this could work and created the first draft of the technical concept/white paper. The WG members commented on the white paper.

The WG comments on the white paper where:

- The service needs to be built on existing infrastructure, be interoperable. It needs to be supported by each publisher.
- 3 areas of attention: authentication, authorisation, service.
- Publishers suggested that the usage statistics on the publishers' content should be reported/fed back to them.
- Caching content was discussed and input from the security team was found important.
- A comparison between the CrossRef and the future eduTDM service was found important. It was also suggested that it needs to be included in the eduTDM white paper.
- Publishers reported that they need to get feedback from their publishing houses with regards to security, authentication and technology works.

6. Third meeting outcome summary

In the third meeting we finalised the white paper, after taking into consideration the WG feedback. We present the white paper below:

In order to propose an implementation plan for eduTDM, it is first important to identify different stakeholders that must be involved in building this service. At present, we can identify at-least 3 such entities:

- i. Individual users (Researchers) interested in scientific text/data mining.
- ii. Universities holding subscription to one or more publishers.
- iii. Publishers that publish electronic copies of scientific content such as journals, conference proceedings, etc. Such content can be open access content or subscription only content.

Having identified the various entities involved, we can now consider the functional requirements for the eduTDM service. We can outline these below in form of use stories.

Functionalities desired by Researchers:

- As a researcher, I want to use a single endpoint so that I can download all content to which my university subscribes to or that is open access using a single API.
- As a researcher, I want to be able to rely on my university authentication mechanism to access content from across publishers.
- As a researcher, I want to have all contents delivered in a uniform format so that I can text/data mine using single (same) pipeline of operations.
- As a researcher, I want to be able to receive incremental downloads so that I can easily update my collection as soon as new content becomes available.

Functionalities desired by Universities:

- As a university, I want to ensure that all my users can text and data mine all subscription based or open access content from all the publishers I subscribe to.
- As a university, I want to have information on usage statistics of eduTDM by my users.

Functionalities desired by Publishers:

- As a publisher, I want to have very minimal or no changes to my existing model of content delivery so that adaptation to eduTDM becomes practical.
- As a publisher, I want to have a secure communication channel so that my content is guaranteed to be delivered to users with valid access rights only.
- As a publisher, I want to have service guarantees so that reliability and efficiency can be ensured.
- As a publisher, I want to have the ability to monitor usage of my contents delivered through eduTDM.

We can now identify the requirements which must be fulfilled by the eduTDM service to meet the functionalities just discussed.

Requirements related to Researchers:

Functional Requirements:

- The service shall provide users with one point of access to get content from across multiple publishers.
- The service shall ensure that only valid users shall be able to issue text/data mining request.
- The service shall aggregate content from all the publishers to which the user is authorised and deliver it.

- The service shall deliver its content in a universal format.
 - The service shall provide users with means to request incremental content such as fetching new content since their last download date.
 - The service shall meet user specified constraints(filters) while looking for matching content to deliver.

Non-Functional Requirements:

- The service shall be able to handle (TBD) number of users per minute.
- The service shall implement (TBD) encryption mechanism to secure content delivery channel to users.

Requirements related to Universities:

Non-Functional Requirements:

- Publishers shall allow universities to use the eduTDM service.
- The service shall not interfere with other activities (services) of universities.
- The service shall be able to provide usage summary to universities on a quarterly/monthly/daily/online basis.

Requirements related to Publishers:

Functional Requirements:

- The service shall guarantee to act in compliance with licenses to the provided content while delivering it to end users.
- The service shall be able to ask for incremental updates of contents from publishers.

Non-Functional Requirements:

- The service shall be able to deliver large amounts of content for TDM without posing a high load on the existing infrastructure of publishers, i.e. protecting existing content delivery models used by human users.
- The service shall be able to provide usage statistics to publishers regarding content accessed from them.

Proposed Design

Our proposal for the eduTDM architecture is motivated by the widely popular solution for internet access across universities -- the eduroam service. eduroam provides its users a common platform to access internet from across a network of universities. Similarly, we would like to

propose the eduTDM framework as a one-point access platform for our users to access content from multiple different publishers for text and data mining.

Fig 1 below depicts the current state of practice which researchers adopt in gathering content from multiple publishers. A user interested in text mining of content from different publishers typically issues separate API calls to each of the publishers, as shown in the figure.

Figure 1: Traditional model of content mining from multiple publishers.

There are, however, several issues that make this practice a cumbersome experience. We outline them below.

1. **Abundance of Publishers:** There are several hundreds of publishers in existence today. Many of them expose their own API endpoints. This imposes two main problems to researchers. First, they need to be individually aware of existing API endpoints and in some cases the content is not available via any API. Second, they need to write and maintain multiple copies of similar queries to issue to each publisher separately.
2. **Heterogeneous Standards:** Different publishers implement different protocols for users authentication and content delivery. Often, this implies that researchers create account on each publishers' platform and ensure that correct authentication tokens (e.g. API Keys) are used when issuing requests to respective publishers. Further, publishers can adopt different standards for content delivery. Therefore, a researcher interested in getting the same type of content, for example on global warming, from multiple publishers will have to write and issue API calls to each publisher in different formats, using different accounts and will receive responses also in a variety of formats.
3. **Workflow Disruption:** From the users' perspective, writing multiple API calls deviates focus from their main line of work. Their main goal of TDM would be better facilitated if there were a direct means of obtaining aggregated content from publishers world-wide.

To summarize, with the existing practice, users are individually responsible for maintaining their system and need to adapt for different publishers and the heterogeneous standards they expose. This is prone to manual error, is limited by domain knowledge of individual researchers and doesn't automatically scale up to accommodate changes/updates introduced by publishers in the future.

eduTDM aims to provide a better alternative for machine access for TDM of content from multiple publishers. Figure 2 below outlines the components of this architecture.

Figure 2: eduTDM vision for scalable content mining from multiple publishers.

In the eduTDM model, users can issue a single API call to eduTDM to obtain all documents matching their need. This will involve a workflow comprising of a sequential series of steps as follows:

- 1) User issues a “request for content” call to eduTDM.
- 2) On behalf of the user, eduTDM issues separate content request calls to each of the publishers or can satisfy the request by means of cached content.
- 3) Each publisher independently processes its incoming request and responds to eduTDM with the requested content.
- 4) eduTDM aggregates and harmonises the content from all the responses received.
- 5) eduTDM responds to the user with the aggregated content.

We can now think about technical solutions that can be used to implement the workflow. For each step of the workflow outlined above, we present our proposal solution as follows (preserving the sequential order of steps in the workflow):

STEP 1

User requests must be supported by means of an API exposed by the eduTDM service. Users must first register to this API to get an API key which will be used in further communications as authentication token. This API shall implement the following features:

- A. Only accept traffic originating from networks of subscribing universities. eduTDM must gather the information on universities' IP address pools when universities first subscribe to use this service.
- B. For each incoming request, extract the information about its originating network (i.e. its IP address). This information is required to fulfill step 2 in the workflow (discussed below).
- C. Allow users to specify filter criteria, e.g. look for partially or completely matching documents on a given topic, get only incremental updates since the last execution, exclude content from certain publishers, etc.

STEP 2

For each incoming request, eduTDM must carry out the following tasks:

- A. **Validate the request:** This shall be based on verifying that the API key used for the query belongs to some registered user of the eduTDM service.
- B. **Create calls to multiple publishers with URL redirection:** At this phase, eduTDM needs to issue content request calls to multiple publishers. This task can be divided into several subtasks:
 - 1. Identify content request fields and filters specified in the incoming call.
 - 2. Create separate copies of query to each publisher: All such copies must contain the document request criteria originally specified by the user but also be specific to meet the requirements of specific publishers. eduTDM must adopt the data request/exchange standards of each publishers to identify the means and format of queries they support for document delivery. As of present, many publishers specify their own API endpoint for text/data mining purposes. In such instances, carrying out this subtask implies that eduTDM shall follow the publisher specific API guidelines and draft an API call matching such specification. In other cases, additional study is required to fulfill this subtask.
 - 3. Enable URL redirection: The next step is to issue those calls from eduTDM to respective publishers. Most publishers already have existing mechanisms to authorise requests based on IP addresses of their subscribing universities. eduTDM can exist independently of any university network and have its own range of IP addresses. Hence, we need a mechanism by which calls forwarded

by eduTDM on behalf of a user are treated the same as originating from the user's university. External services such as EZproxy, OpenAthens and Shibboleth can be used in this task. It should be noted that application scenario akin to our needs already exists within existing infrastructure, although in a different setting. Consider, for example, a user X affiliated to a university U. The university U, in turn, has subscriptions to publisher Z. When X is within the network premises of U, she can freely browse the publications in Z but when X tries the same from the outside world (e.g. a restaurant), the content from Z is inaccessible to her. In that case, X can make use of an external web proxy server (such as EZproxy), which essentially redirects her request through U's network so that the publisher authorises it as a valid request. eduTDM would benefit from having such url redirection facility to authenticate with publishers. Other third-party solutions proposing alternatives to IP address-based authentication are also available; such as the OpenAthens platform. Perhaps a good strategy here would be to discuss our use cases with these vendors and identify the best solution to adopt. URL redirection must be enabled for every incoming request to eduTDM because different users have different access rights to different publishers and eduTDM must ensure that users will only get those contents for which they have legal rights to access.

Both the validation and URL redirection services contribute to the required set of services which eduTDM must implement.

STEP 3

Thanks to the URL redirection mechanism discussed above, publishers receiving requests from eduTDM shall treat them as if they originated from the host university of the original user. To process an incoming request and deliver response, all publishers must individually implement the following services:

- **Authentication:** Authentication is the task of validating incoming requests -- determining whether an incoming request should be processed or not depending upon the credentials it contains. Publishers shall individually perform this task for any requests forwarded by eduTDM and make use of the ip address for authentication.
- **Authorization:** Authorization is task of determining what contents should be accessible to serve an incoming request. It is the responsibility of individual publishers to determine the content access rights for each request forwarded by eduTDM and they should make use of university subscription information to do so.
- **Searching:** Of all the content that is accessible, only those that are relevant should be identified to make up a response for an incoming request. Publishers must, therefore, implement some searching service which determines what contents match to generate response and deliver them.

All these services belong to the set of required services that publishers must provide for eduTDM to function and it is understood that this infrastructure is already in place.

STEP 4

One or more publishers may respond with their content. It is the task of eduTDM to gather contents received from all publishers and deliver the aggregated content as output to the user's API call. We call this as an aggregation service, and it belongs to the set of required services that eduTDM must implement. Text/Data mining API endpoints of many existing publishers (e.g. Elsevier, Springer) deliver their content in XML standard. eduTDM can apply standard parsers to retrieve the content in individual responses and aggregate them to generate the final response to deliver. This response can itself be in one of the several standard document formats (e.g. XML, JSON, etc).

Additionally, we can think of some optional services which eduTDM may implement. These include:

- **Caching:** To reduce workload on publisher's endpoint and to improve user response time, eduTDM could be designed such that it doesn't issue exact same requests to publishers repeatedly. The idea here is that eduTDM could keep a local copy of contents which were obtained from publishers in course of serving past user queries. This cache of documents should be periodically refreshed after a set interval of time.
- **Searching:** For an incoming user query, eduTDM can explore the possibility of generating a response based on its own cache. Provided that the cache contains a local copy of all the content to which the the incoming query has authorization to access, eduTDM can perform the searching service locally. This will help to reduce load on publishers' end point.
- **Usage Monitoring:** eduTDM can maintain a local database tracking the number and type of queries served in a given period of time. This usage statistics can then share with all the stakeholders concerned.

STEP 5

The user receives the aggregated content and proceeds to text/data mining.

In light of this discussion, we can now model the eduTDM architecture in terms of services that are needed for a successful workflow. This is shown in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Services needed for eduTDM implementation.

The key benefits eduTDM offers to researchers over their conventional approach to large scale data/text mining are:

1. **Universal point of access:** Different users from different universities can use this service.
2. **Ease of use:** A single API call to gather content from multiple publishers.
3. **Simplicity:** Users don't need to adapt to multiple publishers' specifications.
4. **Consistency:** The manner in which the users interacts to get documents will remain consistent across publishers and document domains.
5. **Single point of update/change:** To adapt to future changes in publishers' specification, central changes in eduTDM is sufficient; no more custom updates required on every user's end.

Section 7: Direct comparisons with existing services:

Having discussed our model and the TDM workflow it supports, here we want to provide a direct lookup table for easy comparison of eduTDM with other services in use today. Specifically, we want to compare against a) Publisher specific APIs and b) Crossref. Of the former category, many are in existence today while Crossref is the only entity (to our knowledge) that provides TDM support for content across publishers.

Comparison Criteria	Publisher's API	Crossref	eduTDM
Content Across Publishers	No	Yes	Yes
API Output	Metadata + Full Text	Metadata + Link to Full Text	Metadata + Full Text
Accessing subscription-based content	Separate authentication tokens (API Keys) per publisher.	Two-step process -- 1) get fulltext link from CrossRef	Automatic identification of access rights across publishers

		2) issue request per publisher	
Inter-operability	None	Interoperability by Centralization	True Interoperability
TDM Code Maintainability	Users need to update their code to changes in publishers' end.	Users need to update their workflow to adapt to the changes.	eduTDM takes care of updates in publishers' end.
Query support	Mainly DOI matching queries.	Mainly DOI matching queries.	Supports queries for matching different metadata values.

To summarise, we argue for a new model to support researchers in text/data mining content from multiple publishers. We have proposed our eduTDM model as a better alternative to the existing practice and outlined key benefits it will bring to end users. We have proposed a technical workflow to implement eduTDM as a Software as a Service (SoA). We invite all WG members to study this proposal architecture and contribute by providing suggestions, comments or further analysis of the workflow.

7. Fourth meeting outcome summary

Due to a large number of absences - three of the participants were feeling unwell - the fourth meeting was cancelled. The meeting will be re-scheduled for the middle to end of September 2019.

8. Lessons learnt

8.1. Main blockers of quadruple helix co-creation

Due to the short time that was allocated for this co-experiment the Open University involved three actors of the quadruple experiment: Government, Academia and Industry; it was decided though that it would be time consuming to involve the fourth actor, the Civil Society, and that there was not enough time to address this topic adequately to this group.

Even though Civil Society was not included in this experiment, this category will be benefited by the results of the experiment; the white paper will be posted online free of cost with an open license, whereas the tool will be beneficial to those performing text and data mining for non-commercial purposes.

Thus, we could conclude that even though a certain stakeholder type may not be included in the first stages of a project, it would be beneficial not to neglect this group and inform them at a later stage.

8.2. Proposed consensus strategies & co-creation approaches/frameworks

In this co-experiment the OU has extensively used the technological drivers for co-creation. At this very first level, this involved the researchers understanding the publisher and library systems and how machine communication can be achieved. At the next stage of this experiment and during the technical implementation of the tool, apart from the publishers, the researchers would be required to involve the end-users as well, to achieve a human centred design (HCD).

8.3. Most relevant RRI practices (from WP1 and WP2) for the experiment

According to the RRI strength, “to be open to society”, this experiment involved as many stakeholders possible and covered the three out of four quadruple helix actors, Government, Academia and Industry. In addition, the results of this co-experiment, the white paper report will be disseminated to everyone for free via the internet. That way the fourth quadruple helix actor, Civil Society, would get benefited.

8.4. Institutional changes required to fully embed the chosen RRI pillars

The OU co-experiment did not involve any internal to the Open University stakeholders, therefore we do not have anything to report.

8.5. Policy support/changes required to properly embed RRI in the ongoing research with the involvement of the quadruple helix

This co-experiment differed from the other FIT4RRI experiments whose goal was to promote RRI practices within an organisation. The OU experiment attempted to investigate the text and data mining of big scholarly data by conducting the experiment in an RRI way. For that matter, the experiment focused on educating the stakeholders and engaging with them.

From this experiment it became clear that researchers must have an excellent understanding of the stakeholders related to their research question and they must involve as many quadruple helix actors - government, academia, industry, civil society - in the experiment as possible. In addition, it is important to have a regular and clear communication to prevent stakeholder disengagement.

8.6. Any issues/constraints noticed during the experiment implementation (i.e. procedural issues)

This co-experiment was conducted following procedural methods of norm production; for example, it was investigated how publishers operate and which are the needs of text and data miners. In addition, consultation was sought from organisations that make or promote related policies. Issues of organisational and technical challenges were addressed and responses from the stakeholders have been received and analysed.

9. Next steps

With regards to the next steps it is important to specify what is needed from all the stakeholders in order to progress with the eduTDM plan, i.e. funding estimation, time allocation, development resources, discuss security issues. In addition, an overview of the governance, and more specifically the roles, responsibilities and considerations for this effort need to be defined. As this is a project that takes advantage of the UK Copyright exception, it will be initially tested in the UK context, but a further exploration in another country/use case could be tested in the future.

Appendix A – Workshop

The WG meetings were recorded using the GoToMeeting software and the files were saved online https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1P8EpLLuQxfnCwsToH-cSI4RwwD2wP8S_

Appendix B – Experiment KPIs

CODE & INDICATOR			
RELEVANCE			
<i>Scope of the experimentation</i>			
R1	RRI pillars focused upon*	This is a quantitative indicator. It refers to the 5 RRI/OS pillars and the governance of RRI/OS.	Open access, open science, governance.
R2	RRI best practices considered for assessment of their potential implementation in the ongoing research*	This is a qualitative indicator. It refers to the best practices developed under the experiment's design phase which are considered (by the organisation or other relevant actors) relevant and thus deserving to be implemented.	Strong integration with WP1, WP2 practices as shown in the report.
R3	Connection with existing policies/measures developed by the organisation	This is a qualitative indicator. The question is understanding to what extent the experiment is connected with and takes into consideration the existing policies at the organisation level . For example, if there is a budget heading the experiment could refer to, if there is a policy context where the experiment could be framed, etc.	Connection with the library licencing of the text and data mining policies.
<i>Agreement</i>			
R4	Degree of agreement of the beneficiaries about the aims of the experiment	This is a quantitative indicator (a 5-point agreement scale may be used) but also qualitative elements can be collected.	5 (very important for everyone). Interest received. Especially from the working group members – including Elsevier, Crossref, Taylor & Francis – they wanted access to the white paper. Decided not to bring Crossref

		onboard to avoid competition with the other members.	
R5	Degree of agreement of other concerned actors in the organisation about the aims of the experiment	This is a quantitative indicator (a 5-point agreement scale may be used) but also qualitative elements can be collected.	5 (very important for everyone).
R6	Degree of agreement of quadruple helix actors about the aims of the experiment	This is a quantitative indicator (a 5-point agreement scale may be used) but also qualitative elements can be collected.	Civil society was not involved. All other actors fully agree (5). End of the experiment is beneficial indeed for the society.
<i>Mobilisation of internal actors</i>			
R7	Active involvement of the organisation's management *	This is a qualitative indicator, aimed at understanding to what extent the experiment succeeded in involving the top management at the relevant level (e.g., department level, HR offices, University board, etc.). Involvement can be assessed in different ways (participation in meetings and initiatives, meetings with the team, technical and organisational support, etc.)	No meeting yet – however to a certain level yes. Since the project is quite external and based on a very decentralized business model the role of the higher management is not so important.
R8	Active involvement of researchers *	This is a qualitative indicator, aimed at understanding to what extent the experiment succeeded in involving researchers. Involvement can be assessed in different ways (participation in meetings and initiatives, support to the planned actions, etc.)	Good involvement: 3 internal researchers. Further engagement was done through working groups.
<i>Mobilisation of external actors</i>			
R9	Active involvement of quadruple helix actors*	This is a qualitative indicator, aimed at understanding to what extent the experiment succeeded in involving quadruple helix actors. Involvement can be assessed in different ways (participation in meetings and	The actors were involved (besides society).

initiatives, support to the planned actions, etc.)

CODE & INDICATOR	DESCRIPTION	TOOL
EFFECTIVENESS		
<i>Implementation process</i>		
E1 Actual implementation of the planned actions	This is a qualitative indicator, aimed at assessing to what extent the experiment sticks to established plans. Deviations not necessarily refers to problems in the implementation process, but can also be an effort to make the experiment more effective or relevant to the context.	<p>– Monitoring Grid</p> <p>Everything is set – no major delay.</p> <p><Small delay with the first meeting. Afterwards it was mitigated. Delays in composing the shite paper. Four meetings in total – against the 2 planned ones></p>
E2 Compliance with planned schedules and deadlines	This is a qualitative indicator, aimed at assessing to what extent the experiment sticks to established plans. Deviations not necessarily refers to problems with the implementation process, but can also be an effort to make the experiment more effective or relevant to the context.	<p>– Monitoring Grid</p> <p>So far on track.</p> <p><OK></p>
<i>Beneficiaries</i>		
E3 Match between the number of beneficiaries planned/ number of actual beneficiaries	This is a quantitative indicator, the significance of which may vary according to the experiment .	Good match (4). Good interest in the beginning however throughout the meetings some people lost interest. Still 4-5 actors stayed onboard.
E4 Match between the type of intended beneficiaries and the type of the actual beneficiaries	This is a qualitative indicator, the significance of which may vary according to the experiment.	The only category that was not included is civil society (beneficiary). However they will receive all the outputs through the dissemination channels.

CODE & INDICATOR	DESCRIPTION	TOOL
IMPACT		
<i>Objective impact – Institutional agreement</i>		
I1	Number of quadruple helix consensus solutions (common agreed plans/steps) for supporting the embedment of RRI *	This is a quantitative indicator. It refers to the level of involvement of external players in the experiment through formal arrangements. This indicator could be also relevant for the dimension “Sustainability”
		The RRI experiment was somewhat different and it focused mostly on educating the stakeholders. There was not major disagreement among the stakeholders.
<i>Objective impact – Expected changes</i>		
I2	Actual introduction of organisational, regulatory or procedural changes at the level of the research group/department/quadruple helix actors directly involved with the experiment	This is a qualitative indicator. It refers to any significant change in the life of the organisation at the relevant organisational level directly due to the experiment. Any modification observed during and after the implementation phase deserves anyhow to be recorded.
		No specific change. More training actions/seminars introduced. Good internal learning exercise.
I3	Actual introduction of organisational, regulatory or procedural changes in parts of the organisation not directly involved with the experiment	This is a qualitative indicator. It refers to indirect effects of the experiment on other parts of the organisation, which can be viewed as a precursor of an embedment process of RRI/OS.
		No specific change was introduced.
I4	Actual introduction of organisational, regulatory or procedural changes in external organisations (quadruple helix actors)	This is a qualitative indicator. It refers to indirect effects of the experiment on other parts of the organisation, which can be viewed as a precursor of an embedment process of RRI/OS.
		No specific change was introduced (besides the learning path).
<i>Objective impact – Unexpected effects</i>		
I5	Occurrence of unexpected effects concerning the involved actors (e.g. unplanned introduction of new norms, policies, or procedures; establishment of new networks or groups as an effect of the experiment; etc.)	This is a qualitative indicator. Unexpected effects can be both positive or negative, i.e., supporting or hindering the embedment of RRI/OS. When positive, they are considered an important precursor of an embedment process of RRI/OS.
		New collaborations emerged with the stakeholders.
<i>Objective impact – Multiplicative effects</i>		

I6	Observation of result/best practice multiplication in the quadruple helix ecosystem generated through the experiment *	This is a qualitative indicator. Differently from the previous one, which are mainly interested in new actions or reactions, this indicator should capture larger forms of mobilisation on RRI/OS occurred beyond the scope of the experiment.	Ethics best practices; researchers became interested to multiply/replicate the findings. Crossref (external stakeholder) might have been interested. Good interest from the learning perspective – some issues related to whom will lead this.
<i>Objective impact – Communication impacts</i>			
I7	Increased visibility of the experiment within the organisation	This indicator is of a qualitative nature and refers to the presence of information on the experiment or on RRI/OS related issues in, e.g., institutional websites, meetings, newsletters, internal communication channels, and the like. The more the experiment is known, the more is likely to have an impact on the organisation.	Not so much – due to decentralization and the lack of interference among the teams.
I8	Increased visibility of the experiment outside the organisation	This indicator is of a qualitative nature and refers to the presence of information on the experiment or on RRI/OS-related issues because of the experiment outside the organisation.	Yes, due to publications & events.
<i>Subjective impact – Degree of agreement with the experimentation</i>			
I9	Degree of satisfaction of the beneficiaries about the activities carried out	This is a quantitative indicator (5-point scale).	High interest/satisfaction from the interest group members.
I10	Degree of satisfaction of the Teams about the activities carried out	This indicator can be qualitative and can include different aspects.	The team is satisfied.
I11	Degree of satisfaction of the actors internal to the organisation about the activities carried out	This is a quantitative indicator (5-point scale).	Good (4)– but not so often involved.

I12	Degree of satisfaction of the quadruple helix actors about the activities carried out	This is a quantitative indicator (5-point scale).	Very satisfied (5).
I13	Number of RRI best practices evaluated and highly rated by the stakeholders *	This can be a quantitative indicator, even though some qualitative aspects should be anyhow considered (e.g., motivations at the basis of the rating outputs).	Mostly interested in learning about RRI as a whole.
<i>Subjective impact – Changes in the perception of RRI/OS</i>			
I14	Changes in the interest in RRI/OS of each internal actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *	This is a qualitative indicator. It should measure to what extent the experiment raised a greater interest towards RRI/OS, regardless to the orientation (positive of negative), in the internal actors. It is also possible to make the indicator quantitative using a 5-point scale. However, qualitative aspects should be also considered.	In the beginning they didn't know about RRI/OS and then they became interested (towards the end of the experiment).
I15	Changes in the interest in RRI/OS of quadruple helix actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *	This is a qualitative indicator. It should measure to what extent the experiment raised a greater interest towards RRI/OS, regardless to the orientation (positive of negative), in the internal actors. It is also possible to make the indicator quantitative using a 5-point scale. However, qualitative aspects should be also considered.	In the beginning they didn't know about RRI/OS and then they became interested (towards the end of the experiment).
I16	Changes in the awareness of RRI/OS of each internal actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *	Awareness refers here to the attitude of the actors to consider RRI/OS as an important aspect of the life of the organisation interviews are part of. Therefore, awareness refers to a positive orientation towards RRI/OS. This indicator is qualitative in nature but a 5-point scale can be also used.	Yes – became more aware (4).
I17	Changes in the awareness of RRI/OS of quadruple helix actors (at the	Awareness refers here to the attitude of the actors to consider RRI/OS as an	Yes – became more aware (4).

beginning & end of the experiment) *	important aspect of the life of the organisation interviews are part of. Therefore, awareness refers to a positive orientation towards RRI/OS. This indicator is qualitative in nature but a 5-point scale can be also used.	
I18 Changes in the perceived usefulness of RRI/OS of each internal actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *	Usefulness can be considered as a precursor of a future mobilisation in support to the implementation of RRI/OS. It refers to the recognition of the capacity of RRI/OS to address problems that the actors are already dealing with. This indicator is qualitative in nature but a 5-point scale can be also used.	It is more about the usefulness of the learning component (4).
I19 Changes in the perceived usefulness of RRI/OS of quadruple helix actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *	Usefulness can be considered as a precursor of a future mobilisation in support to the implementation of RRI/OS. It refers to recognition of the capacity of RRI/OS to address problems that the actors are already dealing with. This indicator is qualitative in nature but a 5-point scale can be also used.	It is more about the usefulness of the learning component (4).
<i>Subjective impact – Orientation towards future involvement</i>		
I20 Explicit orientation to promote/ get involved in future RRI/OS-oriented activities of each internal actors	This is a qualitative indicator which can be also expressed in quantitative ways through 5-point scales. Differently from usefulness, this indicator assess the personal involvement of the actors in RRI/OS	Since they were not so much involved – therefore this experiment might not have created a momentum.
I21 Explicit orientation to promote/ get involved in future RRI/OS-oriented activities of quadruple helix actors	This is a qualitative indicator which can be also express in quantitative way through 5-point scales. Differently from usefulness, this indicator should measure the personal involvement of the actors in RRI/OS	Similar to the above – since the end product is promoted as a technology – not so much as RRI.

CODE & INDICATOR	DESCRIPTION	TOOL
SUSTAINABILITY		
<i>Recommendations produced</i>		
S1 Policy change recommendations *	This indicator is aimed at measuring the capacity of the experiment to “launch” possible future RRI/OS-oriented policies at the relevant organisational level. This indicator is of a qualitative nature	Nothing observed/mentioned due to the decentralized approach of Open University.
S2 Organisational change recommendations *	This indicator is aimed at measuring the capacity of the experiment to “launch” possible future RRI/OS-oriented changes in organisational practices at the relevant organisational level. This indicator is of a qualitative nature	Nothing observed/mentioned due to the decentralized approach of Open University.
<i>Institutional links and agreements</i>		
S3 Creation of links with key players not previously engaged in the implementation of the experiment	This indicator is intended to assess the capacity of the experiment to activate new possibly permanent social configurations and cooperation relationships. This indicator is of a qualitative nature.	To some extent yes (i.e. Crossref, Elsevier) – through the networks of Taylor & Francis, Jisc.
S4 Creation of stable links with other bodies involved in the implementation of the experiment	This indicator is intended to assess the capacity of the experiment to activate new possibly permanent social configurations and cooperation relationships. This indicator is of a qualitative nature.	To some extent (depends on future funding).
S5 Industry/RFPO proposals for collaboration with researchers *	This indicator is intended to assess if the experiment led to the establishment of clear or possibly formal new cooperation programmes. This indicator is of a qualitative nature.	Potentially yes. Clear strategy for this.
S6 Society-driven proposals for collaboration with researchers *	This indicator is intended to assess if the experiment led to the establishment of clear or possibly formal new cooperation programmes. This	Nothing since society was not fully embedded.

	indicator is of a qualitative nature.	
<i>Institutionalisation processes within the organisation</i>		
S7 Identification/acquisition of new resources to continue the activities or parts of them	This is a qualitative indicator aimed at assessing to what extent the organisation or other internal and external actors are leaned to invest on RRI/OS in the future. This can be a composite set of indicators, also including quantitative indicators (e.g., quantity of resources, number of sources, etc.)	Not yet. Involvement in new proposals.
S8 Establishment of institutional arrangements to make the new operational setups activated by the actions definitive (e.g., institutionalisation of scholarships, drafting of internal regulations that establish procedures to access certain benefits, etc).	This is a qualitative indicator aimed at assessing to what extent the experiment already led to the establishment of new permanent solutions inspired to RRI/OS at the relevant organisational level (department, organisation, etc.).	Nothing observed or mentioned.